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Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Catalogue of Attention and Inclusion Practices for FDP in the EU influence area

Deliverable D5.1

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About RAISD	
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<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

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RAISD Glossary

ARU	Action Research Unit
EC	European Commission
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
HVG	Highly Vulnerable Group
LGTBIQ	Lesbian, Gay, Transgender, Bisexual, Intersex and Queer or Questioning
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
RAISD	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The RAISD project Consortium ‘Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced’ hereby shares its Preliminary catalogue of good (attention and inclusion) practices (Deliverable D5.1). This analysis has the intention to evaluate the work of the following countries in defining and dealing with vulnerable groups VGs of FDP. The partner countries are: Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon.

The RAISD Good Practices analysis has the intention to evaluate past and current inclusion initiatives across the European Union influence area, - characterised in terms of target group, objectives, requirements, type of host community, actual results, evaluation by actors, related artefacts – and to ultimately support the [Action-Research Units](#) in shaping new and innovative [Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies \(TAIS\)](#) for [Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced](#).

The inclusion practices are highlighting numerous connections in terms of helping, assisting, mentoring, educating, and providing services to refugees and vulnerable populations; the selection process included the identification of [actor-oriented criteria](#) that each practice should meet.

All gathered good practices are available at <https://raisd-h2020.eu/observatories/good-practices/> and can be consulted by filtering interest by vulnerability CONTEXT and/or vulnerable PROFILE:

Vulnerability CONTEXT	Vulnerable PROFILE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religion • Language • Housing • Family ties • Medical care • Education • Work • Admin-Legal • Host Community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women • Minors • Unaccompanied Children • Persons with disabilities • LGTBIQ • Elderly People • Pregnant Women • Single Parent, Families with Minor • Victims Human Trafficking • Victims psychological, physical, sexual violence

The classification of VG’s as shown above is respected in general by different countries. It depends on the context they are working in. Some countries are affected by the EU perspective that is described above. Other countries are affected by the UN perspective where VG is related to refugees in general.

Lebanese International University (LIU) through this report will focus on attention and inclusion practices; integration of contributions. All data were gathered from report described by the countries understudy. This

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data will be analyzed to come up with helpful conclusion that will lead the whole project to identify the suitable practices. Most of the data were collected by the ARUs of different countries and other stakeholders.

These tasks included Identifying sources of information, Gathering information artefacts, Analysis of artefacts, Characterise attention and inclusion practices; finally the creation of the catalogue of attention and inclusion practices for FDP in the EU influence area.

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Overview of good practices for all countries

Forced displacement (FD) is a complex process where the identification of needs is difficult and attention practices are challenging to implement. It is also a very diverse phenomenon. People's vulnerabilities depend on each context and vulnerable groups (VG) contrast from region to region. Attention and inclusion practices also varies. However, a common denominator is that if such groups and their specific needs are not properly identified, inclusion practices are not effective. This issue is the key of our RAISD project "Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced". Therefore, one of our first tasks has been the identification of such attention and inclusion practices (Deliverable D5.1).

In general the objectives and methodologies of the investigated countries good practices were fairly stated and quite detailed. Yet, after examining all recognized "good practices" as listed by each country report, it was clear that there is no mutual meaning for them between all nations. Per se, each state approached this definition from its individual and unique viewpoint with numerous connections among these nations in terms of helping, assisting, mentoring, educating, and providing services to refugees and vulnerable populations.

This document -elaborated by LIU- is a compilation of the identified strategies in Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon. The main objective was to have an accurate knowledge of good practices and avoidable practices, in order to latter provide *tailored attention and inclusion strategies* (TAIS) in order to meet VGs needs.

RAISD methodology applies a triangular perspective: Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), action research, and socio-ecological models. All of them are related to the implication of stakeholders, vulnerable groups themselves, and different levels of social contexts and institutions. Thus, sources of information were key stakeholders, vulnerable groups, institutional and NGOs reports and documents as well as literature review.

Yet, in the case of most European nations that were examined, including Turkey and to some extent, Jordan, there were successful at implementing programs to provide safe and dignified environments for incoming refugees and asylum seekers to live dignified lives. One exception is Lebanon, which is a developing country itself and can hardly cope with its massive influx of neighbouring Syrian refugees for the last decade of turmoil and war in neighbouring Syria. Whereas, if we compare Turkey with the rest of the Middle Eastern and mostly Arab countries, one notices a similarity with Europe.

For instance, in **Finland** the good practices largely concentrated on **services** and place Finland as a good option for asylum seekers hoping to secure a better future for them and their families.

Their good practices collectively encompassed providing tailored reception services, which include to some extent special care services, for asylum seekers, give adequate education and safe shelters to unaccompanied children, and also through helping parents in child rearing, by giving them time to rest and entertaining the children though pedagogic activities. Finally, they provide for women living in reception centres meaningful activities in comfortable environments.

For **Italy**, the main focus was on **Education** and **Protection** for asylum seekers, through sixteen good practices. As such, Italy is also considered a good option for asylum seekers hoping for a better future for them and for their families.

Aside from the above stated good practices in Italy, family sponsorship for refugees in Palermo. Council of the Cultures, Municipality of Palermo, high-quality and up-to-date country of origin information for all actors involved in asylum cases, and territorial continuous cooperation network using a comprehensive approach were adopted. Finally, social inclusion processes for unaccompanied children migrant minors in the city of Palermo, and researching female genital mutilation intervention programs linked to African communities, in the EU, were launched as well.

The role of the importance of selecting a role model in the implementing in education youth migrant populations. Furthermore, study approaches that through the success of Palermo in adapting this model, the same methods were applied across five other Italian cities as well. Moreover, similar approaches were done in five other European nations (excluding Italy)-

For **Spain**, the core emphasis was on projects, research and activities based on **cultural mentoring** and **integration** of refugees in the hosting communities comprising practices that place it as another good opinion for refugees or asylum seekers to settle for a better and safer future for them and for their families, somehow like Finland and Italy, but focus of somewhat different approaches. For this regard, in Spain this was evidenced with its good practices. Aside from the aforesaid good practices, Italy, Spain, Romania agree that Agricultural Job Rights to End foreign workers Exploitation are a must.

The good practices in Spain discuss collectively discussed issues about motivational campaigns addressed to young mothers. They also reflect on the ways to address the vulnerable communities' needs, use trainings and workshops, and always put the beneficiaries' need and interests first. Finally, in Spain through evaluating collectively their good practices encompass researches based on a rights approach, as well as on how the beneficiaries' accessed the centre as per the agreement. Last but not least, the gender approach is encompassed as well.

For **Lebanon**, the primary emphasis was on **Protection** and **Assistance** of vulnerable populations, which interconnect with the good practices recognized by **Italy**. One could summarize the information on Italy's good practices, in order to mention the main points related to Lebanon. Yet, for **Hungary**, the primary emphasis was on **Integration** and **Outreach**. Yet, its practices show that.

Based on the available information, Hungary, many of the practices were implemented through counselling, mentoring and coaching sessions, with special asylum procedures to assist in integration. Although there weren't always communication procedures adopted for each of its practices collectively, there was an overall follow up with beneficiaries.

For **Jordan**, the main focus was on **Humanitarian** projects, which somehow intersect with humanitarian activities identified by **Italy**. The nature of these good practices are therefore, similar to Italy's. Overall, Jordan aims to: 1) Assist in providing education and vocational trainings to the refugee communities from some of the neighbouring countries. 2) Work towards providing job opportunities for members from those communities, via

skilled building or other capacity buildings trainings. 3) Update its latest socio-economic data, and in providing recent figures for providing work permit visa for refugee workers. 4) Measure social cohesion. And, 5) provide the beneficiaries with specific ICT skills in pursuing higher education and to equip them with relevant technological and entrepreneurial skills for assisting them in the 21st century world (i.e. 21st Century Skills).

Turkey accustomed to this kind of migration flows adapted certain practices for compulsorily evacuated people. Yet, For **Turkey**, the main focus was on **Education** and **Support** forcibly displaced people, including children free access to educational services, educational brochures and booklets, free health services, support centres, and establishment of refugee rights commission.

Among the good practices in Turkey, yet excluding those aforementioned, there are associations they have established themselves and centres either supported by the State or through NGOs supported centres. These practices—mostly cater for the large influx of Syrian and other refugees, and for properly preparing and training the personnel in charge of handling their needs, as per the first two good practices.

Turkey's good practices on entrepreneurial skills are similar to those of Italy's but also cater for women entrepreneurs' needs. The good practices covering gender equality are somewhat similar to the practices adopted by Spain. One can be pretty sure that Turkey's usage of good practices are quite progressivism in nature, and are, to some extent in the region quite modern, in comparison with the other Near Eastern countries. This seems to become evident with Turkey's good practices related to adopting GBV trainings and helping in achieving women's rights.

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1 Policies, laws and treaties affecting attention and inclusion strategies towards VGs of FDP

1.1 Policies regarding VGs

In this part of the analysis we will compare the different policies affecting attention and inclusion towards VGs of FDP established by the 7 countries: Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon. We will try to look at the policies of each country to see what criteria was adapted in defining the VG's. In addition, to compare the different policies, laws and treaties that were legislated or agreed on in order to define VG's with all inclusion strategies.

The context of each country understudy has a major effect on the policies, laws and treaties affecting attention and inclusion strategies towards VGs of FDP. The EU context affects the two countries Italy and Spain in their legislation process towards VG's, yet Finland has another perspective and focus on issues that appears more important for them in terms of instant needs like the integration of the VG's in the social context of the community. The Middle Eastern countries like Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon are affected by the UN perspectives. Lebanon and Jordan dealt since 1948 with Palestinian refugees with the help of the UN so their legislations are affected by the UN trends. However, Jordan tried to meet the EU criteria in providing more details when dealing with the different VG's. Hungary is discussing the VGs legislations as whole group without providing details.

Italy, Spain, and Jordan defined well the basic needs of vulnerable people. Italy provides a sophisticated framework in a separate excel sheet that describes extensively the needs of vulnerable people. Spain defined needs in relation with the different types of vulnerable people. Jordan describes in a table the basic needs and the potential actions that can be done to address each one. Finland is still in the process of defining vulnerable people and their needs. Turkey discusses the issue of needs in general and focuses on the language and communication. Hungary did not address the issue. Finally, Lebanon tackles the issue from the UNHCR perspective but did not discuss it in detail.

Only Italy and Spain address the issue of adaptation. Italy focused on the intercultural adaptation in addition to the communication dialogues. The adaptation in Spain is focusing only on the number of vulnerable people that may reach a mass influx where programs and services need to be reinforced. The rest of the countries did not address this specific issue clearly.

All the countries, other than Jordan and Lebanon, are states parties to the 1951 Geneva Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol. The EU's Common European Asylum System is also based on the principles in the Convention. States parties to the Convention are required to protect refugees that are in their territory and to obey to the principle of non-refoulement — that is, to not return refugees to places where their life or freedom would be threatened on account of race, religion, nationality, membership in a particular social group, or political opinion. In practice, the states parties to the Convention vary significantly in their receptivity to asylum seekers and the extent to which conflicting national policies affect adherence to norms prescribed in the Convention.

Asylum seekers are required to submit an asylum application to the country's competent authority. Different actions apply to different categories of applicants—for example, those applying for asylum upon

arriving at the border versus those applying from outside the country through the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), or those applying for refugee status versus those applying for humanitarian protection. The Convention permits divergent practices in the processing of applications. Screening requirements that involve collecting personal details, fingerprints, and photographs of the applicant are common. The determining authority typically examines submitted documentation and interviews the applicant.

Denied applicants commonly have the opportunity to appeal an adverse determination. Assistance to Asylum seekers includes housing, food, access to medical care, education, employment, travel documentation, and information about their legal rights.

In conclusion, Italy and Spain have clear policies affecting different VG's. Those policies deal with VG's as defined by EU. Finland although it is part of the EU, yet it is still hesitant in defining the VG's. It legislates policies only for the following VGs: Unaccompanied Children, disabled, human trafficking and language minorities. Hungary did not provide laws or policies to address the issue from the EU framework or any other perspective and discuss the issue from the broad perspective same as Turkey and Lebanon. Jordan made significant efforts to address VGs as described by the European Union, yet it addresses only: Children, Unaccompanied Children, people with People with disabilities, elderly, women, single parents and Health issues. So, legislations still differ from one country to the other based on the context of each. It is recommended to cooperate to benefit from each country experience to provide more details laws and treaties that help in reaching more specific groups of VGs.

1.2 Implementation of the strategies and policies

In this part of the analysis, a comparison between partners at the level of the implementation strategies is done. The comparison will address the implementation plan at the level of each type of VGs.

Italy and Spain are members of the EU, their plans are affected by the EU definition of VG's. So, they classify the VG's the same way as of the EU recommended. Finland, although it is part of the EU, it hesitates in defining the VG's so it focused only on some traits like the issue of language. Countries in the Middle East like Jordan, Lebanon and Turkey are affected by the Syrian refugees' waves so their perspectives of the plans focused on planning to provide basic needs. Especially that both Jordan and Lebanon have experience based on dealing with Palestinian refugees. Jordan tried to adapt their perspective to an EU one yet still it needs more work on the policies to include all types of VG's. Hungary is still not clarifying well its position and doesn't elaborate extensively the strategies and policies.

Italy provides clear implementation National plans that tackle most of the different types of VGs. **Spain** put into action several laws, protocols and Royal decrees that deal with VGs needs and management. **Finland** is criticizing the process of identification of victims and consider it as inadequate at the national level. However, Finland established centres to welcome and help VGs hoping to define precisely in the future the actual description of VGs. **Jordan** included a complete implementation strategy with the collaboration of the UNHCR and tried to meet in its implementation plans most of the VGs. Turkey just mentioned in its plans the duties of

the Migrations institutions in case of mass influx. **Hungary** and **Lebanon** did not address the issue in terms of plans but as a type of cooperation with NGO's UN institution to provide help to refugees in general.

Italy identify the levels of actions in a systematic way:

1. Practices and activities meeting the needs of the Highly Vulnerable Groups, in a direct or indirect way.
2. Beneficiaries' satisfaction on basis of levels of integration and increased adaptability to new hosting environment
3. Procedural benchmarking to determine advantages and limitations of the implemented practices
4. Efficiency of organizational impact and cost-effectiveness, in order to include key aspects of perceived quality.
5. Impact assessment of the long-term effects, transferability, and sustainability of the proposed good practices.

Spain put plans in action to meet VG needs: implement training actions aimed at officials and public employees of the Local NGOs related, among others, to the following issues: Registration, Basic services (social intervention programs), Schooling processes, and Occupational Training.

Generate spaces for participation of all social actors aimed at exchanging experiences and promoting joint actions aimed at promoting social inclusion, preventing risk situations, and promoting citizen coexistence in the local environment.

There is local level variation in how work and study activities are organised in Finland. In practice, in many centres work activities comprise cleaning or repair work in the area of the reception centre and study activity mainly Finnish language lessons. However, recently there have been attempts to develop statutory work and study activities to be more diverse and to take people's capabilities better into account. Furthermore, there have been some temporary and regional projects by NGOs, institutes of higher educations and private companies aiming to support asylum seekers employment opportunities. However, many of those are targeted mainly to skilled persons.

In the local level, in some reception centres, there are many extra activities and services organised for asylum seekers. These might include, for instance, various group activities, sporting activities and relatively extensive language tuition (e.g. chapter 3.1.5). Some of these activities are provided by centres themselves, but often by civil social organisations or volunteers. It is also stated that churches have had a central role in integrating asylum seekers to Finnish society. The strong role of the civil society is related to the fact that municipalities have no legal obligation to integrate asylum seekers, but only migrants who have already received a residence permit.

Jordan identifies for every need a specific activity:

1. Protection:
 - a. Iris-scanning fraud-proof biometrics for refugee registration.
 - b. psychosocial support and emergency cash assistance to SGBV survivors
 - c. implementation of prevention activities such as women empowerment workshops, self-defence classes led by refugee women and various awareness activities within communities

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2. Basic needs:
 - a. Shift from the distribution of in-kind relief items to the provision of humanitarian cash assistance.
 - b. Refugees receive cash through iris-scan biometric technology directly through bank ATMs.
3. Health:
 - a. UNHCR provides comprehensive primary, secondary and tertiary health care services free of charge for refugees in Zara and Zaatari camps,
 - b. for vulnerable Syrians in urban areas and for all non-Syrians in urban areas
4. Education
 - a. UNHCR's Albert Einstein German Academic Refugee Initiative program (DAFI) is the primary conduit for tertiary education.
 - b. UNHCR is also collaborating with the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA)
5. Community Empowerment and Self Reliance
 - a. Following the London Conference on the Syria crisis in early 2016 and the issuance of the Jordan Compact, the Government of Jordan waived the fees required to obtain a work permit for Syrian refugees in a number of occupations open to foreign workers and simplified the documentation requirements
6. Durable Solutions
 - a. Number of Syrian refugees are resettling outside
7. Access to Energy
 - a. UNHCR's main goal in Jordan's Syrian refugee camps is to ensure that all refugees can satisfy their energy needs for cooking and lighting in a safe and sustainable manner, without fear or risk to their health, well-being, and personal security.
 - b. In line with Jordan's strategy to become a green economy by 2020, UNHCR provided access to clean and renewable energy in refugee camps, as Jordan is now home to the first refugee camp in the world powered by renewable energy.

Hungary and Lebanon did not address the issue of practices in their report.

Treatment of vulnerable people by different countries are mentioned in a moderate way, Italy focus on the different cultural background, Spain treats them as one homogeneous group, Jordan treats them as foreigners, Turkey, Hungary, and Lebanon did not address the issue.

The inclusion process is given much attention in Italy due to a basic European financial support, in addition to an Italian National plan. In Spain, the inclusion process is still pending by the authorities as described by their report. Finland is using the definition established by the European court of human rights to define vulnerability in order to elaborate on inclusion strategies. Jordan is getting the help of the UNHCR and the livelihoods partners to get economic support for the inclusion process. Turkey and Hungary did not address the issue and Lebanon discusses the inclusion process in general and not specifically for vulnerable people.

In conclusion, the implementation plan differs from one country to another; this is because the criteria are not clear for all of partners how to address their policies; in addition, the definition of the VGs is seen differently by RAISD partners. Some countries are influenced by the EU perspective like Italy, Spain and Finland,

and others by that of the UN like Jordan, Turkey, and Lebanon. It is recommended to agree on one criterion of the VG's and try to address it specifically to reach a constructive conclusion that will help in unifying the policies, plans and practices.

1.3 Formal and Informal care practices from the host or transit communities

In this section we acquired a framework as a road map to assess the following variables: Typology and characteristics, Religious groups along with civil organizations relating to each of the following countries: Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Jordan, and Lebanon. Based on the presented data it is an absolute necessity to adopt a policy framework driven by social justice and equity; moreover, developing a prototype inspired by UNHCR would create a pathway among civil organizations to better empower VGs on many fronts such as: education, health, and social assistance.

Typology and Characterization: The case of Typology and Characterization is most likely similar with respect to Jordan and Hungary, which stated that typology and characterization could be implemented by religious groups, civil organization, unofficial groups, and neighbourhoods. They could be formal in the sense that they have a planification (program or project) but they do not have public or international funding. However, there is a common case in accordance to Finland, Spain and Turkey presented information where no applicable information where collected with this subject matter. Moreover, findings resulting from Lebanon and Italy disseminated similar results where vulnerable groups are well followed by both national and international partners.

Religious Groups: In the case of the following countries Finland, Spain, Lebanon, and Turkey presented results marked high resemblance in which these groups are totally not considered in the previously stated countries. Unlike Hungary, Jordan, and Italy were compiled data revealed that religious groups receive neither public nor international funding.

Civil Organizations: Worldwide assistance programs addressing VGs heavily rely on the work and practices of civil organizations. Accordingly, to the work of civil organizations, data presented on the following countries: Finland, Italy, Spain, Jordan, and Turkey revealed that the civil organizations sector solely concentrates on the attention and inclusion of asylum seekers along with VGs. It is very imperative to shed the light on the activism done by UNHCR which closely coordinates the refugee status under the leading and collaborative efforts of governments in cooperation with the private sector.

Assistance/Empowering programs could be entailed with vocational training, skill development programs, and entrepreneurship programs.

However, in accordance to Lebanon in relation with the work of civil organizations data was not presented.

Mapping on the Formal and Informal care practices from the host communities

The Mapping on the Formal and Informal care practices from the host communities show no clear definitions of the following practices for Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, and Lebanon, as Mental disorders, torture and rape and other gender violence were not clearly defined. On the other hand, only Jordan has defined rape and other gender violence as “One of the missions of UNHCRR in Jordan is to eliminate sexual and gender abuse and achieve gender equality”.

2 Vulnerable Groups' (VG) experiences

2.1 Identification of potential good practices

Worldwide, good practices revolve around the availability of specific adequate variables such as: accessibility to quality education, inclusion in the workforce, housing and settlement, and social network along with gender sensitiveness. Pledging a commitment towards attaining valuable good practices by VGs requires governmental policies addressing their social and economic inclusion.

Regarding literature review, a “good practices” is defined as approaches, experiences or initiatives that work well and can be replicated elsewhere, with techniques and methods that produce effects and results, considered to be effective in contributing to refugees welcoming and integration, and therefore deserving to be disseminated and proposed to other organizational contexts(IUL, 2018). Moreover, bearing this definition in mind, the good practices were selected based on eight criteria which the practice should meet. The criteria were discussed and agreed upon within the PandPAS partnership, at a project meeting. They are described as follows:

Technical feasibility, Efficacy and success, Respect of the human rights and equity framework, Reliability and adaptability, Inherent participation, Network coordination, Gender sensitiveness, Innovation, Awareness, Education, Employment, Entrepreneurship, Governance, Housing and settlement, Political and public participation, Social Network and welcoming.(IUL 2018).

Starting by technical feasibility, the good practice is easy to learn and is possible to implement. Moving forward to efficacy and success, the good practice has proven its strategic relevance as one effective way in achieving a specific objective. It has been successfully adopted and has a positive impact on refugees and communities, followed by Respect of the human rights and equity framework the good practice reflects the basic universal principles of human rights law, humanitarian law, and refugee law. Taking into account the local contexts, the practice aims to reinforce rights granted to all refugees through these instruments (e.g. the right to freedom of movement, the right to education, the right to recognition before the law, the right to work, the right to health care and the right to access public services) and also seek to protect vulnerable individuals and groups who are at heightened risk of human rights violations. Nevertheless, the good practice is flexible and has the potential for replication and is adaptable to similar objectives in varying situations, which may mean different local or national contexts is reflected by Reliability and adaptability. The good practice improves collaboration between professionals, institutions, and citizens in what concerns implementation, follows a participatory approach, by promoting meaningful participation of refugees and migrants, and supports a joint sense of ownership of

decisions and actions was under the name of Inherent participation. Moreover, the good practice under the name of Network coordination was involves approaches of collaborative governance, and a community of practitioners that may include municipal authorities, community-based groups such as refugee associations, faith organizations, local professional networks, business owners, academia, humanitarian organizations and the participants in the good practice. Giving the importance of Gender sensitiveness, its good practices was explained based to gender equality, considers the specific gender realities of women and men, and integrates gender issues into all aspects of the initiatives. Moving forward to Innovation, the good practice encompasses innovative efforts on refugees welcoming and integration shows innovative thinking and contributes to an innovation in the livelihoods of participants. In the mapping of good practices carried out by the partners, nine areas of action emerged as more frequent. These are not exhaustive since they do not cover all the needs regarding migrant and refugees' integration. Moreover, they are not exclusive, meaning practices often have more than one area of action in their scope. For the purpose of this collection, the practices were organized according to the dominant or most distinctive area of action. The areas are as follows.

Governance was considered *as good practices with coordination and cooperation among integration actors, comprehensive and coordinated policies, enhancing processes of sharing information between key partners in place. Nevertheless, the awareness campaign via the Centre for Peace Studies initiated the choir and at the moment supports its activities through an EACEA project. Campaign" Dobri domain"; which focused on collecting donations to support young migrant artists, also decided to give a donation to the choir and the main goals of this good practice is cultural exchange and promotion of integration and diversity through music. Moreover, the awareness campaign was also Implemented by several countries Thus, the project was coordinated by the French organization L'âge de la Tortue, which works in the visual arts field. Designed by Paloma Fernández Sobrinho, the initiative has an artistic and experimental dimension, with the aim to create an encyclopaedia in paper version and in digital version with approximately 400 testimonies made by migrants. The Encyclopaedia format was chosen in this case in order to disseminate non-scientific knowledge, resulting from life experiences, with all the subjectivity that this involves. The main idea was to gather diverse testimonies of migrants that could be the source of a new knowledge, based on the intimate and the individual. The testimonies of migrants have the peculiarity of having a specific format, as each protagonist wrote an intimate and personal letter addressed to someone they left behind in their country of origin.

The governance campaign was also adopted by IOASI. OAS is a network that carries out actions addressed to asylum seekers and refugees. In 2002 the network joined SPRAR System, a National Network for Protection of Asylum Seeker, and Refugees. OASI project supplies services of welcoming, integration and legal assistance. The network provides 19 places and accepts people sent by SPRAR Central service, Local Prefecture and Police Office. Personal Projects last 6 months, extended up to 12 months in case of vulnerability. The services provided are the following. Welcoming Services: accommodation, food, pocket money, clothes, and support to daily needs; access to territorial services (social, educational, health); information about Italian society and local context, civic and citizenship education, organization of social services; language support. Integration: access to Italian advanced class; individual support in drawing personal path based on professional skills; professional orientation; support in job seeking: enrolment to national job centre (Centro per l'Impiego), application for job position; support in access to professional training; support in job placement; support in independent housing solutions; support to social inclusion; permanent psycho-social workshop; didactic path in secondary school.

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Legal counselling: psycho-social and health support to all beneficiaries, particular focus on vulnerability; legal and administration desk focused on all kind of documents and relations with local institutions.

Based to the world health organization, the MENA countries have also adopted several practices in Jordan, Lebanon, and many other countries. Such practices were known as national legislation for the protection of domestic workers, promoting gender equality and empowering women rights, providing health services to refugee, migrant and host populations, addressing social protection needs for vulnerable children. However the good practices that were adopted in Lebanon explained via Promoting the right to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health, equality and non-discrimination of refugees and migrants, Provision of equitable access to UHC, including access to quality essential health services, medicines and vaccines, and healthcare financing for refugees and migrants: , Expansion of the PHC centres network ensuring quality standards, Access to secondary and tertiary health care, Provision of short- and long-term public health interventions to reduce mortality and morbidity among refugees and migrants, The expanded program of immunization, Malnutrition screening and management, Screening for non-communicable diseases: Providing reproductive health services, Addressing mental health issues: , Strengthening the health system, reducing morbidity and mortality among refugees and migrants through short- and long-term interventions, Support to strengthening health services, expansion of the National Early Warning and Response System (EWARS), Improving adolescent and youth health through supporting school health programmers, Addressing violence against women and girls, Emergency shelter for women and girls , Protecting Domestic workers (UNHCR, IOM, ILO, 2018).

Quite often the asylum seekers are satisfied in the overall level of reception centre quality in Finland. According to the Finnish case, decentralized housing, activities provided either the reception centre, voluntary workers or some other organization which take asylum seekers outside the centre and promote integration to local communities, having a worker responsible for employment of asylum seekers providing help in finding employers and counselling in issues related to Finnish labour market and right of asylum seekers in work, and developing a specialized unit for Unaccompanied Children minor asylum seekers securing access to educational system and other services, promoting leisure participation and providing relatively intense support in schooling, emotional issues and everyday life present the very essence of good practices by VGs. However, in Spain vulnerable people engage more likely in social work. Further with the Lebanese case data acquired have stated that the LCRP is aligned with the following key processes and frameworks such as: Regional Refugee and Resilience Plan, and UN Sustainable Development Goals. However, results relating to Jordan were more personalized based on individual experiences and opinions. Moreover, no present data was available relating to Italy, Spain, and Hungary.

Mapping on good potential practices by Vulnerable Groups (VGs)

The good potential practices by Vulnerable Groups (VGs) in Italy, Spain, Finland, and Turkey, for Torture, Rape and other gender violence and Other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence are not considered, and Not Available for Hungary. Yet, for Jordan and Lebanon, the general good potential practices by Vulnerable Groups (VGs) are also not classified.

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2.2 Recommendations for new or existing practices

Worldwide, good practices revolve around the availability of specific adequate variables such as: accessibility to quality education, inclusion in the workforce, housing and settlement, and social network along with gender sensitiveness. Pledging a commitment towards attaining valuable good practices by VGs requires governmental policies addressing their social and economic inclusion.

In the following, the desired practices by asylum seekers in Finland majorly request more extensive language tuition, more extensive and systematic childcare, and better access to healthcare. Likewise, to the Spanish case where Projects for the empowerment of foreigners with comprehensive care needs, to provide resources and tools to migrants that improve their access to standardized protection systems are a must unlike Turkey where some of the interviewees made recommendations for cultural events involving people from both communities. Stepping forward with Lebanon, where major recommendations suggest the importance of scaling up delivery mechanisms that offer clear benefits to all vulnerable communities and expand partnerships to improve the quality of implementation It is imperative to mention that data relating to this subject matter were collected neither in Hungary nor in Jordan.

Mapping on the Recommendations or proposals for new or existing programs/practices

The Mapping on the Recommendations or proposals for new or existing programs/practices for Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon for VGS such as Children, Unaccompanied Children, People with disabilities, Elderly, Gender, Pregnancy, Human Trafficking, Serious Illness, Mental disorders, Torture, Rape and other gender violence, and Other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence were Not clearly Defined

It is imperative to mention that the recommendations stated provide new dexterities with viable gains; however they are not closely relating to those labels stated in the table, they're more likely stated in a general manner and not only oriented into a specific sector such as women or children.

2.3 Practices to be avoided

Practices to be avoided when addressing vulnerable groups (VGs) are mostly related to the asylum processes in the majority of the tackled countries. These processes encounter prolonged asylum procedures, insufficient informing and distanced asylum investigation, these processes were cited by top priorities through VGs shared experiences and stories. It has been observed that unfair policies relating to education, healthcare services, decent employment opportunities and social security represent the very essence of what practices to be avoided.

From literature review a concluding remark is that conflicts and wars are key turnings in all migration and sectarian tension. Globally speaking, the most vulnerable are in general Palestinians and Syrian refugees who lack the least ingredients towards a dignified life, usually when we characterize a group as vulnerable that means they don't have access to their basic human rights whether education, health benefits or the ability to really integrate in the workforce. In most countries just as the case of Lebanon, which is struggling with economic crisis, national health coverage for their own people, and then these vulnerable groups become a

secondary priority where they are not given the attention and the care that they deserve. Unfortunately, this is the case for all the vulnerable groups in Lebanon and most under privileged countries. When it comes to the roles of social institutions regarding migration and forced displacement, it is referred to: education system; job market: religious authorities; mass media: judicial sphere; police/ security. All of these have an important role to play. Unfortunately, all of these are preoccupied with channel issues and national crisis management so none of them are doing what they are supposed to do especially when it comes to undeveloped countries just as the case of Lebanon, Turkey and Jordan (Jamali, 2020). When addressing the advocacy practices tackled in support for Syrian refugees, civil Society is the only player that has been active consistently and trying to do what they have to do visa vice the Syrian refugees. Yes, they literally have history, competent, commitment, and they have been doing their best to fill the gaps that have come from policy makers or national institutions. They have acquired an interesting sense of relationship with an essence of compete-collaborate; in some cases, they try to collaborate, but the element of competition is always there (Jamali, 2020).

Taking into consideration the current health crisis relating to COVID 19, accommodating environments now they feel more likely feel that we need to take care of ourselves and this is their top priority for now; they literally believe that they have to take at first of their families and kids. Sadly, the situation we're going through is working against the Syrian refugees and all refugees as well (Jamali, 2020).

Consequently, legislations and lawmakers play a pivotal role in attaining the elimination of segregating practices amongst refugees or generally VGs, these may include:

1. Combating segregating national systems for unaccompanied groups such as integrating them in the workforce and national social security programs. (UNHCR, 2020)
2. Challenging harmful social norms and practices and promoting positive norms and Champions of change towards protective practices (within families, communities, social Spaces), gender equality, including women empowerment and positive masculinity stronger child agency and participation. (UNHCR, 2020)
3. Elimination of all forms of segregation amongst the youth in terms of education and vocational trainings. (UNHCR, 2020)
4. Eradication of conflict sensitivity, gender, persons with disabilities, youth, and environment. (Jamali, 2020)

From a comparative perspective, according to the case of Finland, the practices to be avoided according to the VGs experience are most likely relating to the reception system along with poor availability and quality of work and study activities, poor access to health care services, deficiencies in accommodation services, and the lack of childcare services. This is not the case of Turkey in which asylum seekers support primarily depends on NGOs. However, due to the increasing number of refugees, the number of these centres has become insufficient. For this reason, asylum seekers demand that the number of these centres must be expanded. Furthermore, with Italy, Social inclusion practices that contribute to aggravate or legitimize any of the below specific interaction difficulties should be avoided; a classical example could be regulations, ordinances, and provisions of local administrators explicitly or covertly xenophobic. Stepping to conclusion with Spain, Hungary, Lebanon, and Jordan where data relating to practices to be avoided where not stated.

So, the mapping on the practices to be avoided according to their experience for Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan, and Lebanon for Children, Unaccompanied Children, People with disabilities, Elderly, Gender Human Trafficking, Serious Illness, Mental disorders, Torture, Rape and other gender violence and Other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence were Not clearly Defined.

3 Stakeholders' experiences

3.1 Identification of potential good practices

After reviewing the “Stakeholders experiences” sections submitted by all participating countries, it is noticeable that the identification of the good practices depends on the type of the activities established by the stakeholders. For example, **in Finland**, reception system experts and professionals are the stakeholders who named several already existing good practices within the reception centres and imagine some practices that could be feasible in the future. For **Italy**, good practices were identified following the proposal of Manfred Max-Need’s Fundamental Human Scale Development (1989) which provides an overview on potential Italian Good Practices that contributed to satisfy needs, while increasing self-reliance and a balanced interdependence of beneficiaries with the inclusion-environment. For **Spain**, the identified good practices have been compiled as they have been considered as such by other specialized sources and ARU members in different ARU Workshops. Most of them are in general address to asylum seekers and refugees with no distinction on vulnerabilities or vulnerable groups. For **Lebanon**, ARU team members identified the good practices based in the responsibilities of role of the Lebanese government and the NGOs. For **Jordan**, NGOs and INGOs in Jordan are crucial stakeholders who appeared at the beginning as philanthropist mediums. Following the socio-economic and political challenges that Jordan encounters recently relating to the refugee crisis, stakeholders has played and still play a remarkable role in integrating, refugees with people in the host country as well as presenting developmental projects and services including legal assistance (ARDD-Legal Aid) health care (SAMS), after-school programs (UNHCR), and financial support for tertiary education(DAFI). For **Turkey**, Turkish government and NGOs were the main stakeholders. For **Hungary**, the ARU team is the main stakeholder who identified the list of good practices.

The following countries succeeded in providing information about the identification of potential good practices by the partners of the Consortium.

After going over all identified good practices as listed by each country, it was obvious that there is no common definition for the term “good practices” among all countries. Each country approached the term from its own different perspective with many intersections between these countries in terms of helping, assisting, mentoring, educating, and providing services (health, etc...) to refugees and vulnerable populations. For example, **Finland** focused on mainly on **services** such as restricted availability of services vs. individual support, Baseline interview and register data, social work and holistic knowledge, Work for/with families, investing in remedial services and preventive activities, practices related to language tuition and recreational activities.

For **Italy**, the main focus was on **Education** (youth and mothers) and **Protection** for asylum seekers such as bringing young mothers back to education, socio-labour integration paths for Unaccompanied Children foreign minors and young migrants, Health centre for asylum seekers and refugees, integrated transcultural

intervention for psychiatric care, legal clinic for human rights, protection of migrants and their prolonged detention in hotspots, humanitarian corridors as a legal and safe alternative, social and entrepreneurial capacities of migrant women, mentoring and vocational assistance for migrant youth, high-quality and up-to-date country of origin information for all actors involved in asylum cases, trafficking of Women for Sexual Exploitation.

For **Spain**, the main focus was on projects, research and activities based on **cultural mentoring** and **Integration** of refugees in the hosting communities including Intercultural youth mentoring programme in Spain, Programme for Equal Treatment and Anti-Discrimination, Universities leading research and training for the integration of refugees, Connect Migration Network – Digital Literacy for Immigrants, Emigrational Project on the media's treatment of immigration and asylum in Spain, Program Women, Health and Violence 2013: 'Women's health in women's hands', Transnational Observatory for the Refugees' Resettlement in Europe (T.O.R.R.E.), Grundtvig Project: European Language Portfolio with immigrants, refugees and asylum seekers (IMPORT), Training and Certification Linguistics Programme for Immigrant Workers, LETRA (identified via a study undertaken by the Committee of the Regions).

For **Lebanon**, the main focus was on **Protection** and **Assistance** of vulnerable populations, which intersect with the good practices identified by **Italy**. The practices include ensuring protection of vulnerable people, providing immediate assistance to vulnerable populations, support service provision through national systems, and reinforcement of Lebanon's economic, social, and environmental stability.

For **Jordan**, the main focus was on **Humanitarian** projects, which somehow intersect with humanitarian activities identified by **Italy**. These projects are based on collaboration with Jordanian government. Their main concern include monitoring and identification issues that the Jordanian government had failed to address sufficiently, advocate policy solutions to local challenges, easy access to and share of information about Refugees, Syrian refugees, VGs and FDP between stakeholders, researchers, public and private sectors and government, Support and find financial aid to sustainable and prosperous projects (educational, psychosocial, health, empowerment and other basic needs) targeting Refugees, Syrian refugees, VGs and FDP, assistance of Syrian refugees in camps and in urban areas, ensuring that VGs have access to a quality education, health care, psychological support, empowerment, and legal aid, cooperation to defend Human Rights, fight terrorism, help victims of war and support refugees in Jordan, provision of vocational training and job placement, as well as income-generating activities for Refugees, Syrian refugees, VGs and FDP, raising awareness and engage in national dialogue to bridge the gap between refugees and host groups.

For **Turkey**, the main focus was on **Education** and **Support** of forcibly displaced people including children free access to educational services, Educational brochures and booklets, free health services, support centres, and establishment of Refugee Rights Commission.

Mapping of identified potential good practices with vulnerable typologies

For Italy, only other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence are considered. There is no information for torture and Rape and other gender violence. Spain and Turkey dhow no information for Torture; Rape and other gender violence and other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence. Whereas, Finland, Jordan

and Lebanon point out that Generic Good practices are not classified for Torture; Rape and other gender violence and other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence.

Note: Spain, and Turkey have also identified other potential good practices that are not classified against the listed typologies. For Turkey, the generic practices focused on access to education and preparation of educational brochures and booklets, establishment of refugee rights commission, and the provision of free health services. For Spain, the generic practices dealt with programs for intercultural youth mentoring, equity, discrimination, integration of refugees, job rights, and linguistics training.

3.2 Recommendations for new or existing practices

After going over and analysing the recommendations or proposals for new or existing programs presented by all countries, the following observations can be made:

- There are no specific common aspects across the recommendations of all countries. This is due, as observed from analysing all recommendations, to the difference in the Priorities, ultimate goal, and approach adopted by the concerned stakeholders.
- There should be a common terminology to be used by all concerned countries. For example, forcibly displaced people, refugees, migrants, and vulnerable people are used interchangeably.
- Recommendations of some countries intersect in terms of generic programs such humanitarian helps, services to refugees.

For example, a significant intersection was found between **Lebanon** and **Turkey** in terms of programs that help people dealing with vulnerable groups to treat them with equity, psychological support, peace, and avoiding any kind of exploitation and abuse. **Italy** and **Turkey** intersect in programs that deal with preparation of vulnerable groups and the people that are dealing with them.

For **Italy**, the main focus was on programs that **prepare** and **empower** refugees to be part of the host communities by preparing beneficiaries for employment, enhancing and recognizing previous learning experiences, empowering income generation for target beneficiaries, following a culturally sensitive and gender oriented approach, ensuring fair accessibility to territorial inclusion-service environment, facilitating individuals' adjustment with the national integration systems' environment, promoting own ethnic community engagement, pursuing a policy for orientation, mentoring and tutoring of beneficiaries, fostering comprehensive interdisciplinary of territorial Networking and Cooperation, promoting an increase in female participation, promoting social promiscuity of both, local and foreign HVG participants, pursuing a personal and social development policy, pursuing a supporting policy for specific social Vulnerable Groups. For **Lebanon**, the main focus was on humanitarian programs including equity in humanitarian action, avoid harming, peace and stability, partnership, and prevention and response to sexual exploitation and abuse. For **Turkey**, the main focus was on programs that stress on increasing aid for orphans and disabled people, creating an immigrant policy, investment in crisis areas, promotion of cultural and adaptation activities, provision of psycho-social support for staff working with vulnerable groups, local media education, and increase of health services.

Italy

- The practice prepares beneficiaries for employment.

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- The practice enhances and recognises previous learning experiences.
- The practice includes empowering income generation for target beneficiaries.
- The practices follow a culturally sensitive and gender-oriented approach.
- The practice ensures fair accessibility to territorial inclusion-service environment
- The practice is offered in accordance with institution capacities.
- The practice facilitates individuals' adjustment with the national integration systems' environment.
- The practice and procedures are easily comprehensible, and their objectives are clearly defined.
- The practice provides that affective and psychological assistance is guaranteed.
- The practice promotes own ethnic community engagement.
- The practice pursues a policy for orientation, mentoring and tutoring of beneficiaries.
- The practice fosters comprehensive interdisciplinary of territorial Networking and Cooperation.
- The practice promotes an increase in female participation.
- The Practices promotes social promiscuity of both, local and foreign HVG participants.
- The practice pursues a personal and social development policy.
- The practice is society based for a more effective and sustainable response by the whole community.
- The practice is organised in such a way as to ensure efficiency in management.
- Inclusion practice pursues a supporting policy for specific socially Vulnerable Groups.
- The practice design is based on operational flexibility.

Lebanon

- Equity in humanitarian action
- Do not harm
- Peace and stability
- Partnership
- Prevention and Response to Sexual Exploitation and Abuse

Turkey

- Increasing aid for orphans and disabled people
- Creating an immigrant policy
- Investment in crisis areas
- Cultural activities
- Adaptation activities
- Psycho-social support for staff working with vulnerable groups - Local media education
- Increasing health services

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Mapping of recommendations or proposals for new or existing programs with vulnerable typologies.

The following twelve practices were identified: Children, Unaccompanied Children, and People with disabilities, Elderly, Pregnancy Human Trafficking, Human Trafficking, Serious Illness, Mental disorders, Torture, Rape and other gender violence and other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence. But, not all of the seven countries identified them all. For Italy, only, Gender and Other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence are considered. For Spain, Finland, Hungary, and Jordan information of the practices are not available. For Turkey, only Unaccompanied Children and Other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence are considered. In the case of Lebanon, only Rape and other gender violence and other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence.

Note: Italy, Lebanon, and Turkey have also recommended or proposed new or existing programs that are not classified against listed typologies. For Italy, the proposed programs deal with employment, empowering, accessibility to territorial inclusion-service environment, and integration, promotion of ethnic community engagement, orientation, mentoring and tutoring of vulnerable groups. For Lebanon, the proposed programs deal with equity in humanitarian action, peace and stability, partnership with vulnerable groups. For Turkey, the proposed programs deal with for orphans and disabled people, immigrant policies, cultural and adaptation activities, and increasing health services.

3.3 Practices to be avoided

The careful examination and analysis of the contributions of Italy, Lebanon, and Jordan tackled different practices to avoid has led to the following observations:

- A great deal of difference was observed among practices identified by different countries.
- It is clear that the stakeholders did not follow a common procedure for the identification of practices to be avoided.
- For each country, it is not obvious which ultimate goal the proposed practices to be avoided serve. For example, do they serve inclusion practices, empowering and integration of vulnerable groups, etc...?
- These practices should be proposed based on the feedback and experience of the stakeholders with different vulnerable groups taking into consideration the context, and the situation of the different VGs.

For **Italy**, the main focus on avoiding **social inclusion practices** that contribute to legitimize, perpetrate or aggravate any of the following specific challenges and needs including persisting downward labour inclusion and segregation in the low-wage, unprotected sectors of the labour market, persisting barriers to education and specialized training, lack of access to political and citizenship rights, lack of migrant political representation and upward social mobility, emergence of a xenophobic and nationalist discourse targeting migrants, erosion of solidarity among the migrant population, disruption of the Italian refugee reception system due to the new Security Law, and discrimination and abuse of power.

For **Lebanon**, the main focus was on **Dignity** which is considered as a pervasive concept in humanitarian discourse, though it is almost always undefined. Only by understanding Syrians' own definition of dignity can the

humanitarian response be judged to either uphold or undermine their dignity. For displaced Syrians interviewed for RAISD, dignity was consistently evoked in their conceptualization of rights, respect, and independence – concepts that were legal or refugee status. Consequently, the practices to avoid according to their criteria are the ones that touch their dignity in a negative way.

For **Jordan**, the main focus was management of services to refugees including roles, services, and projects provided by stakeholders, services that do not meet the quality promised by stakeholders, absence of a good management to services in some cases, lack of trust between stakeholders and beneficiaries which to the most extent results in access to false information, imposing the program of external donors without considering the needs of the beneficiaries, unqualified staff that run developmental and humanitarian projects affecting the satisfaction of the beneficiaries.

Italy

- Social inclusion practices that contribute to legitimize, perpetrate, or aggravate any of the below specific challenges and needs should be avoided.
- Persisting downward labour inclusion and segregation in the low-wage, unprotected sectors of the labour market.
- Persisting barriers to education and specialised training.
- Lack of access to political and citizenship rights.
- Lack of migrant political representation and upward social mobility
- Emergence of a xenophobic and nationalist discourse targeting migrants.
- Erosion of solidarity among the migrant population.
- Disruption of the Italian refugee reception system due to the new Security Law.
- Discrimination and abuse of power

Lebanon

- Dignity is a pervasive concept in humanitarian discourse, though it is almost always undefined. This study sought to examine dignity in displacement, starting with the affected community – displaced Syrians in Lebanon – by asking, ‘What is dignity to you?’
- Only by understanding Syrians’ own definition of dignity can the humanitarian response be judged to either uphold or undermine their dignity.
- For displaced Syrians interviewed for this study, dignity was consistently evoked in their conceptualization of rights, respect, and independence – concepts that were legal or refugee status.

Jordan

- Sometimes, civil society challenges and questions the roles, services, and projects provided by stakeholders.
- Sometimes, services do not meet the quality promised by stakeholders.
- Absence of a good management to services in some cases.
- Lack of trust between stakeholders and beneficiaries which to the most extent results in access to false information.

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- Sometimes, refugees adhere to participate in developmental service and projects if there is no financial aid presented at front.
- Some of the external donors impose their program without considering the needs of the beneficiaries.
- Sometimes, unqualified staff runs developmental and humanitarian projects affect the satisfaction of the beneficiaries.
- VGs sometimes are not the main target of most of the presented projects and plans.

Mapping of practices to avoid with vulnerable typologies.

The Mapping of 'Generic practices to avoid' with vulnerable typologies in Italy, Jordan and Lebanon , for Children, Unaccompanied Children, People with disabilities, Elderly, Gender, Pregnancy Human Trafficking, Human Trafficking, Serious Illness, Mental disorders, Torture, Rape and other gender violence and Other serious of psychological physical or sexual violence not classified. Yet, For Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey are not considered.

Note: Italy, Lebanon, and Jordan have also listed practices to avoid that are not classified against listed typologies. For Italy, the list of practices to be avoided deal with social inclusion practices be avoided including downward labour inclusion and segregation in the low-wage, unprotected sectors of the labour market, barriers to education and specialised training, discrimination, and lack of rights. For Lebanon, the practices to be avoided deal mainly with dignity. For Jordan, the practices to be avoided deal with civil society challenges, lack of good management and trust between stakeholders and vulnerable groups, unqualified staff dealing with vulnerable groups.

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4 Identification of potential actor-oriented key criteria

4.1 *Evaluating policies and practices towards Vulnerable Groups (VGs)*

Introduction

In this part of the analysis, we will search for criteria to evaluate the policies and practices of attention towards VGs and FDP. Not all the partners provide clear criteria for the evaluation process, yet Italy, Spain and Jordan tried to consider the most important points that can be used as indicators to assess how the practices and inclusion can best be provided to VG's.

The following are the different indicators provided by two of the partners from a participatory perspective with key stakeholders: Italy and Spain.

Italy

Evaluation by VGs' on the positive effects of inclusion experiences highlights that the practices should:

- Allow to improve life conditions, not only from an economic viewpoint, but also in terms of relational capital.
- Allow to develop language skills and technical-vocational skills, sometimes also enhancing past training experiences (formal and non-formal).
- Allow an opportunity for immediate income and be oriented on the self-awareness of one's employability.
- Help the recipients to build a perception of their employability and increased their autonomy in searching for opportunities after the conclusion of the apprenticeship.

Spain

Rights perspective. It implies entitlement. It is recognised in the own EU directives.

Participation perspective. Inclusion must be characterised by participation. What means: The capability and the right to participate, or at least being consulted. It is related to a greater autonomy -which is promoted by all sort of programmes and organisms.

Accountancy perspective. Towards the beneficiaries of programmes. After you value needs and interests of a participant, priorities are established, and usually an "personal integration plan" is designed and agreed. It should be evaluated regarding what objectives have been fulfilled.

Empowerment perspective. It is related to the guarantee of entitlement. Again, the rights' perspective regarding international protection is a basic reference. There is a failure to comply with the law and EU directives. Capability mechanisms must be put in place.

Information. Huge critiques about current situation. Information must be available, clear, and accessible from all points of view.

Quality. The lack of transposition of the recast Qualification, Asylum Procedures and Reception Conditions Directive (Directive 2013/33/Eu) is seen as a disadvantage for any public policy, or private practice. The same is for the lack of regulation (*reglamento*) for the Law 12/2009 of 30 October 2009.

Process perspective. Inclusion is a process; therefore, the system must be flexible and adapted to VG needs. Training and education are key part of such process.

In conclusion, the point addressed for each country regarding the evaluation criteria were set based either on the needs like **Jordan** or on life condition, language, employability and autonomy like in the case of **Italy** and finally based on rights, participation, accountancy, information, empowerment and quality like in the case of **Spain**. So, the evaluation process is still not clear, it has different perspectives yet the common points that we can conclude is quality of services afforded and empowerment of the VG's.

4.2 Common features for compatible criteria

In this section we will try to reach a threshold for the minimum standards. The criteria are shown below:

Italy

- Set a common quality framework for inclusion strategies and services tailored to Highly Vulnerable Groups.
- Enable the assurance and improvement of quality inclusion strategies for HGV.
- Support mutual trust, thus facilitating recognition and stakeholders' long-term cooperation, building a safe community around the highly vulnerable target groups along the inclusion process.
- Provide information on **quality practices and community integration service providers**.

Spain

- What should the social "context" be like in which a good practice or a successful inclusion strategy is developed?
 - A social context that has to and can be reviewed in order to work on diversity. Do we really accept diversity?
 - Today's society teaches us to coexist, but not to live together. An ideal social context would be a host society that really welcomed migrants.
 - A context that favours being part of a community in every way. The system rewards the similar ones and punishes the different.
- Accessibility requirements / problems, what should we pay attention to?
 - Transparency and unifying criteria are basic. Accessibility means that we are accessible. A reception and referral service that is effective beyond the speciality of the NGOs.
 - We must continue providing services but focusing on human rights, not resources. We fit/adjust people into **resources, and not resources to people (this latter is the way it should be)**.
- Performance procedures and forms of care, what differences and what requirements does "individual" versus "personalized" imply?
 - To personalize is to listen to them, follow them up, and accompany them personally.

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- Customizing (personalizing) is taking into account the specific needs of these people, it implies flexibility in the projects.
- Individualizing **would only follow administrative procedures.**
- Principles of action, and values, what should we consider? (ethical principles, social intervention values, norms, standards)
- That the human being is the centre of the process, not the economic resources. Promote people's ability to choose and meet their specific needs.
- Avoid bureaucratization.
- Put people with their differences on the centre of attention. Asylum seekers must have decision-making power over their own lives, and the right to be wrong.

Jordan

- Targeting by displacement status: Evidence calls into question the practice of using IDP/refugee versus host population as a targeting delineation in humanitarian programming in urban contexts, where there may be significant underlying vulnerability and poverty among resident populations.
- Using locally derived assessment tools: Many reports stress the importance of local insight to the process of informing vulnerability assessments whether developing a brand-new context-specific scale or adding locally relevant indicators to a pre-existing tool. Evidence from both gender-based violence (GBV) and food security assessments supports developing entirely new scales or adapting scales with local data.
- Categorical targeting: Evidence shows that, while targeting by category of person using demographics such as gender or age can be useful, it must be context specific. Defining vulnerable groups by demographic identifier must ensure that those classified are truly the most in need of a humanitarian intervention.
- Using pre-existing administrative data: Use of pre-existing administrative data must consider that it will often be imperfect in its representativeness, how it was collected and how up to date it may be. Given rapidly changing urban environments and disruptions caused by the crisis itself, pre-existing administrative data should be used with caution, bearing in mind the need to determine the supplementary secondary data needed for identifying vulnerable populations.
- Self-targeting: Evidence indicates that the self-targeting method is expensive and difficult to maintain long-term or to transition to local authorities. Self-targeting through a physical centre is unlikely to reach the most vulnerable who wish to remain hidden.
- Community-based targeting: Evidence reveals some success in identifying the most vulnerable through community-based targeting, which leverages local knowledge and contextual understanding – critical to urban response. The evidence also shows that to avoid bias, a nuanced understanding of the community, motivating factors for participation and local power dynamics is required.
- Using a sampling frame: Evidence indicates that the density and heterogeneity of cities necessitates larger sample sizes, more clusters, or smaller geographic units during data collection to ensure pockets of vulnerability and diversity are captured to inform targeting.

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In conclusion, the common criteria for the evaluation of the practices are based on categories of VG's, quality, and context of the practices. So, the minimum standards for dealing with VG's is to focus on collecting information from the VGs, the classification of information based on the different types of VGs and provide quality type of practices.

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5 Identification of potential good practices

5.1 Characterisation of practices

After reviewing and analysing the characterisation of the practices identified by the all-participating countries, the following observations can be made:

- The process of identification of stakeholders that made an identification of the practice is not described by each country
- The process of identification, selection, and characterization of the practices is not well established.
- Practices are recommended to be characterized in terms of addressed needs, target groups diversification, specific goal, scope, or level of impact (local, regional, national) and typology of intervention. This approach was adopted by Italy
- The interviews with a large population of vulnerable groups should represent the bedrock of the process of identification of practices.
- Identified practices did not tackle all classified vulnerable groups (children, Unaccompanied Children, etc.) and this is due to the lack of a common process for the identification and characterization of practices.

The practices identified by each country are presented in tabular format to consider the logical relationship between the practices and the target vulnerable groups. The countries are Finland, Italy, Spain, Hungary, Jordan, and Turkey. Also, a detailed excel sheet is provided to map the practices identified for all country with vulnerability context and profile.

Good practices FINLAND

IDENTIFIED UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

#	Practice	Target Vulnerable Group	Aim of the inclusion practice
1	The assistance system for victims of human trafficking	Victims of human trafficking	To make sure that the rights of trafficking victims are enforced and fulfilled and in the case of asylum seekers, provide tailored reception services.
2	Minors' units	Unaccompanied Children minors	To offer necessary shelter and protection to unaccompanied minors. Provide age-sensitive care, education and support.
3	The unit of intensive assistance	Asylum seekers suffering from mental disorder	To provide statutory reception services as housing, social and health services, work and study activities, reception allowance and interpretation. The services are tailored to people with mental disorders and who consequently are in need of more intensive support.
4	Childcare service	Asylum seeking families with small children	To offer parents of small children free moments without the children, for instance, to take part in work, study or other activities or take care of

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Identified by CESIE

6	Protection of migrants and their prolonged detention in hotspots	Unaccompanied Children minors, women travelling alone or pregnant women, people who have suffered physical or mental trauma, sick or disabled people	To offer a worthy welcome together with guidance and inclusion services in dedicated facilities to the most vulnerable people among migrant population.
7	Humanitarian corridors as a legal and safe alternative	Vulnerable asylum-seekers: in addition to victims of persecution, torture and violence, families with children, the elderly, the sick, people with disabilities	To avoid boat trips through the Mediterranean and to grant people in "vulnerable conditions" legal entry into Italian territory with a humanitarian visa and the opportunity to apply for asylum at a later date.
8	Social and entrepreneurial capacities of migrant women	Migrant or refugee women living in Palermo, from Senegal, Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Morocco, Tunisia, Syria, and Chile	To promote the social and entrepreneurial capacities of migrant women through development and exploitation of food-related knowledge and skills that provide possibilities for income-generating activities.
9	Mentoring and Vocational Assistance for Migrant Youth	- Mentees: youngsters with migrant background/from ethnic minorities. - Mentors: adult people with migrant backgrounds	To create role models for migrant youth or youth from ethnic minorities throughout of the vocational career, by understanding the needs of young people and local contexts.
10	Family sponsorship for refugees in Palermo	Unaccompanied Children, migrants who have already left the reception system but are not completely independent	To achieve autonomy and positive inclusion of vulnerable groups through reception in local families as a path of integration and active citizenship, by sharing spaces and experiences, enhancing reciprocity and autonomy.
11	Council of the Cultures, Municipality of Palermo	Foreigners, community and non-community nationals, stateless persons and those who have acquired Italian citizenship residing in Palermo	To collaborate with the Municipality in providing the necessary support to foreigners, individuals and associated to enable the effective exercise of all forms of participation or access to laws and regulations documents for residents.
12	High-quality and up-to-date country of origin information for all actors involved in asylum cases	Decision-makers in the field of asylum, lawyers, legal aids, international protection agencies, and agencies involved in asylum cases (in the Italian case it's the Territorial Commissions) + Applicants for international	To secure easy and fast access to high-quality and up-to-date country of origin information for all actors involved in asylum cases, contributing to a fair, effective and efficient refugee status determination procedure.

Identified by CESIE

		protection (any person who, outside his or her country of origin, files a request for international protection in another State, or has expressed his or her will to do so)	
13	Territorial Continuous Cooperation Network adopting a comprehensive approach	Unaccompanied Children migrant minors	To intensify and expand a functional and efficient cooperation for supporting the autonomy processes of children and ageing-out youth from the residential centres.
14	Social inclusion processes for Unaccompanied Children migrant minors in the City of Palermo	Unaccompanied Children minors and migrant young adults	To strengthen, test and evaluate innovative pathways to sustain unaccompanied minors' transition to adulthood, by offering them a series of educational experiences such as training opportunities and work placement, as well as independent housing solutions.
15	Trafficking of Women for Sexual Exploitation	Human Trafficking Victims	To widely investigate the role of organized crime - international and local - as a determining factor of drive and attraction for the victims of trafficking linked to sexual exploitation.
16	Researching Female Genital Mutilation Intervention Programs Linked to African Communities in the EU	Women and migrant communities that are still practicing Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) in Europe	To empower and motivate FGM affected communities through community leaders, influential people and peer group champions to challenge the social norm supporting FGM.

Good practices SPAIN

Identified by UCM Universidad Complutense De Madrid

#	Practice	Target Vulnerable Group	Aim of the inclusion practice
1	Guidance and Accompaniment for the Social Integration of the Immigrant	Population of foreign origin and general ommigrant population	To provide attention to newly arrived immigrants, immigrants with a long process of staying in Spain with difficulties or doubts when carrying out administrative procedures, both social and legal, and native population, in general, mixed

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Identified by UCM Universidad Complutense De Madrid

	Population		marriages or people who want to employ people in irregular or nationalized situations.
2	Integral and Emergency Reception Program for People and Families in Temporary Protection Regime in Spain	Families with minors, people without family support and in an emergency situation, migrants in situations of high vulnerability	To provide attention, support and emergency accommodation, on a temporary basis at the Mejía Lequerica Municipal Shelter, to applicants and beneficiaries of international protection, until they can access the social protection provided by the national asylum system and migrant people in a situation of high vulnerability.
3	Solidarity of Responsibilities: an experience of awareness, training, and networking	Childhood, gender and LGTBIQ+	To train and sensitize professionals and authorities involved in the process of integration of vulnerable groups (children, trafficking and LGTBI + people) potential beneficiaries of International Protection from an approach of childhood, gender diversity and human rights
4	Evaluation of impact (ACCEM)	Administrative situation not resolved, ignorance of the language and culture of the host country, People with disabilities, lack of resources, unemployment, victims of gender violence, victims of trafficking, etc...	To know the impact on the beneficiaries of their participation in the International Protection system; to establish the precise adjustments for the improvement of the intervention and to raise proposals for improvement of the International Protection system.
5	Caritas Diocesan of Madrid (Cáritas Madrid)	Migrants at risk of residential exclusion.	To encourage family recovery and autonomy (self-development) through temporary accommodation as part of the integration and stabilizing process.
6	MAP - Marco de Atención a las Personas (Framework of Attention to People)	Families with dependent children, the elderly, people with serious illnesses and others.	To give a prompt response to the demands and needs of people in a comprehensive manner covering all areas always counting on person's competences and accompanying them in their way to be self-sufficient.
7	CON-VIVIENDO the municipality: a process of inclusion of refugees in the municipalities of the Community of	Diverse VGs (and non-VG migrants).	To promote the processes of inclusion of applicants for international protection in the municipalities of the Community of Madrid, improving access to housing, social rights and general services in equal opportunities.

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Madrid			
8	District Action Teams	Diverse VGs (and non-VG migrants).	To improve the quality of life, social cohesion and territorial rebalancing in the Districts of Centro, Chamberí and Tetuán, through the regeneration of the urban environment and the dignification of the common space.
9	Transversal work teams in the territorial delegation of CEAR Madrid	Professionals working with VGS	To improve intervention with migrants and refugees in areas of work that are transversal to the services, so that the beneficiaries of the CEAR Madrid projects will have a significant, direct or indirect participation in this practice.
10	Relational volunteer model	Diverse VGs (and non-VG migrants)	To Promote supportive relationships between local and migrant citizens, through close and personal support that gives refugee and migrant people new tools for social inclusion. The model is based on the company and active listening, favoring a stable relationship over time
11	Madrid for all	Newcomers to the system and people whose programs end, and they are deprived of basic resources (gender perspective).	To collect the resources offered by the 21 districts of Madrid; but it has a vocation of being replicated in other locations: Mapping of free resources and autonomous access for refugees and migrants
12	Integral and Emergency Reception Program for People and Families	Asylum Seekers and vulnerable migrants in Temporary Protection Regime and Migrants in Extreme Vulnerability Situation in the Municipal Shelter of Mejía Lequerica”	To provide emergency accommodation and basic needs coverage at the Mejía Lequerica Shelter, to international protection applicants and migrants in situations of vulnerability or social emergency during their stay in the city of Madrid.

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Good practices HUNGARY

Identified by Menedék

#	VG	Aim of the inclusion practice
1	Let's work together for integration All refugees	To enhance the accessibility of services for different immigrant groups: bridging an information gap between local governance and civil society members (service providers)
2	Refugee outreach Isolated individuals	To offer individual casework and social counselling in Budapest focusing on the individual needs and problems of refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection (i.e. general support in communication between refugees and authorities, employers, flat owners and utility companies in order to prevent or manage intercultural or language conflicts, as well as legal counselling to refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection).
3	SOS Refugees Families, children	To provide a complex assistance for refugees at various stages of the asylum procedure: Healthcare and social care to refugee families and minors at various locations (refugee reception centres, families' temporary shelters, and reception facility for unaccompanied minors).
4	Women, adolescent clubs Women, adolescents	To monitor specific needs (and vulnerabilities) and to inform adolescents and women about services available for them (at other service providers).
5	Building bridges All refugees	To enhance the integration of third-country nationals in the city of Budapest, by providing support for building the capacity of the local administration to develop and implement local integration strategies, to set up migration information points, and to establish partnerships with non-governmental organizations (NGOs).
6	YOUNIG All refugees	To lay the foundations of a local immigrant integration framework in a town where there was no such thing before: After a screening of local needs and local services, several pilot interventions were implemented: Front office and back office staff training in topics related to immigration, specific training to kindergarten teachers about

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Identified by Menedék

7	Protect	PTSD patients	<p>integration of foreign children.</p> <p>To develop an easy-to-use tool for PTSD diagnosis: Used by staff members of service provider institutions for a first diagnosis of PTSD among refugees. A very short - 15 minutes - training enabled service providers to become familiar with the questionnaire, and consequently they could use this tool for monitoring PTSD symptoms among their clients.</p>
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Good practices JORDAN

Identified by Yarmouk University

#	Jordan	VG	Aim of the inclusion practice
1	VET & HE Program for vulnerable Syrians and disadvantaged youth from host communities	3000 young Syrians (mainly in the age group 18-24) in Syria and disadvantaged youth in host countries in the region (Iraq (KRG), Jordan, Lebanon, Turkey) as well as disadvantaged youth from the host communities	To provide equal access to further and higher education in the region for Syrian youth who have finished their Tawjihi exam (Secondary School Certificate) in Syria or in the neighboring countries without being able to continue their University studies or had to abandon their studies because of the war and displacements.
2	Improved access to sustainable livelihood opportunities	Syrian refugee women, vulnerable youth and host population members residing in Bani Kananah and North Mazar/Irbid	To improve the socio-economic by building their skills and experience to better identify and access job opportunities and build their capacities to plan and manage their own income generating initiatives.
3	Revision of Jordan transitional interim country strategic plan	Food-insecure Syrian refugees and Syrians stranded at the north-eastern border between the Syrian Arab Republic and Jordan	To update Socio-economic data in Jordan since the latest figures on poverty, food security, nutrition and related sectors pre-date the start of the current crisis in the (Berm).
4	The Work Permit Initiative for Syrian Refugees in Jordan: Implications for Policy and Practice	Practitioners implementing livelihood and related programming for Syrian refugees in Jordan following the February 2016.	To provide a critical overview and analysis of the implementation of the work permit initiative for Syrian refugees in Jordan. Also intended for general public, in academic and policymaking fields, who are interested in livelihood programming and work permit initiatives for refugees.
5	Syrian Refugees and	Jordanian and Syrian parents	To measure social cohesion in the Jordanian

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Identified by Yarmouk University

	Social Cohesion in Jordan	who had developed perceptions of one another based on contact through their children's schooling. Participants were Jordanian factory workers.	context and to gain a cursory understanding of providing a limited worker rights to Syrian refugees in Jordan
6	TEFSR – Transferring E-Business Fundamentals to Syrian Refugees (Training practice)	Syrian refugee and host community	To provide Syrian refugee and host community with skills that can allow them to pursue several web and commerce related higher education degrees in both ICT and economic colleges, or/and start their own businesses
7	Competency-based Career Focused Training	Syrian and Jordanian Students in Northern Jordan	To equip and empower audiences with relevant technical and hot/needed topics, knowledge, soft skill and entrepreneurship skills to enable refugees and the Jordanian population to blend in the local market demand.

Good practices TURKEY

Identified by Anadolu University

#	Practice	Target Vulnerable Group	Aim of the inclusion practice
1	Education program for healthcare providers (SIHHAT Project)	Forcibly displaced people under temporary protection, healthcare providers	To support and develop basic health services already provided by the Ministry of Health for the Syrians under temporary protection in Turkey.
2	Media Training on Refugee Coverage	Forcibly displaced people in Turkey, media workers in Turkey	To inform media workers in Turkey about the issues when dealing with forcibly displaced groups
3	Women Cooperative for women from the host community and forcibly displaced women (SADA Women's Cooperative)	Forcibly displaced women living in Turkey (Syrian, Afghan, Iraqi, Persian) - Turkish women	To build an entrepreneurial spirit in women under temporary protection. Meso: Improvement of the sustainability of social cohesion among forcibly displaced and women from the host community.
4	Photography workshop for people under temporary protection and from	Forcibly displaced women living in Turkey (Syrian, Afghan, Iraqi, Persian) – General public, university students in Anadolu	To raise awareness about the importance of intergenerational dialogue and intergenerational, intercultural, cross-institutional and intergovernmental collaboration in achieving

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Identified by Anadolou University

	the host community (Light the Dark Photography Exhibition)	University	gender equality and social cohesion between forcibly displaced and the host community.
5	Women and Girls' Safe Space (WGSS)	Forcibly displaced women and girls	To socialize and re-build their social networks; Receive social support; Acquire contextually relevant skills; Access safe and non-stigmatizing multi-sectorial GBV response services (psychosocial, legal, medical); Receive information on issues relating to women's rights, health, and services.

Good practices LEBANON

Identified by LIU Lebanese International University

#	Practice	Target Vulnerable Group	Aim of the inclusion practice
1	WHO's Contribution to the Health Response: Main Projects	Vulnerable, displaced Syrians.	To reinforce quality primary and secondary health care, reinforcement of communicable diseases monitoring, early warning and response system, and equipping health facilities and supplying vaccines and medicines.
2	Enabling Job Resilience and Protecting Decent Work Conditions in Rural Communities Affected by the Syrian Refugee Crisis in Northern Lebanon	Rural employment, community development, local economic development, agricultural development, agriculture, refugees.	To create productive employment through local economic development and sustainable enterprises in northern Lebanese communities affected by the Syrian refugee crisis.

Note: Italy, Spain, and Finland have also list of good practices that are not classified against listed typologies. For Italy, the practices deal with, Education, socio-labour integration paths for Unaccompanied Children foreign minors and young migrants, health centres and services, human rights and protection, marginalized persons, mentoring and vocational assistance for youth. For Spain, the practices deal with reception programs, responsibilities, residential exclusion, vulnerable groups with serious illnesses, professionals working with VGS, volunteering work, resources for refugees and migrants, and protection of asylum seekers and vulnerable migrants. For Finland, the practices deal mainly with establishing activities for women.

5.2 Formal and informal Practices to be avoided

After careful examination of the formal and informal practices to be avoided, as listed by each country, it is clear that these practices were not developed based on a well-defined procedure context or common criteria. For example, the process of identification of the stakeholders who made the identification of practices is not common across all countries.

Selection criteria need to be established for the sake of preparing the floor for a successful and fruitful communication with the vulnerable groups, asylum seekers, refugees, etc... Getting in direct contact with these groups opens up the door for a realistic selection, listing, and classification of the practices to be avoided. A large population and consequently a large number of vulnerable groups should be involved to cover as many practices to avoid as possible. This approach was adopted, to a certain extent, by Spain during the 4th meeting of the Spanish ARU. Representatives from NGO NGOs, public administration, forced displaced and vulnerable social groups, education and academia attended the meeting. Involving forcibly displaced people and vulnerable social groups had led to the identification of some of the practices to be avoided.

The identified practices are presented in tabular format for a consistent and harmonized presentation of these practices.

Practices to be avoided, identified by Italian ARU

#	Practice
1	Social inclusion practices that contribute to legitimize, perpetrate, or aggravate any of the below specific challenges and needs should be avoided
2	Persisting downward labour inclusion and segregation in the low-wage, unprotected sectors of the labour market
3	Persisting barriers to education and specialized training
4	Lack of access to political and citizenship rights
5	Lack of migrant political representation and upward social mobility
6	Emergence of a xenophobic and nationalist discourse targeting migrants
7	Erosion of solidarity among the migrant population
8	Disruption of the Italian refugee reception system due to the new Security Law
9	Discrimination and abuse of power

Practices to be avoided, identified by Spanish ARU

#	Practice
1	"I prefer two years in jail than two months in the CIE [detention centre]", since there are no rules and there are no rights, there are also very bad conditions in centres for Unaccompanied Children minors"

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Practices to be avoided, identified by Spanish ARU

2	Another bad practice would be the privatization of asylum seeker services
3	In the case of minors, the violation is maximum if they are not provided with documentation or schooling

Practices to be avoided, identified by Jordanian ARU

#	Practice
1	Start questioning immediately without developing rapport
2	Start questioning without finding out if the person has time
3	Use closed (e.g. crossed legs and arms) or threatening (e.g. towering over or pointing) body language or avoid eye-contact
4	Take all the notes yourself – it will prevent you engaging effectively with people, and you may not be able to decipher them later
5	Miss opportunities to learn in greater depth, even if it means spending more time
6	Structure the interview around the order of your checklist points, for example “Now I would like to ask you about...”
7	Miss opportunities to gather more detailed information from certain people for the sake of always covering all check-list points
8	Use closed, leading or ambiguous questions
9	Review and record note each night while they are fresh in your memory, and check relevance of checklist
10	Leave notes until you cannot remember what they meant or discover you should have asked more about an important issue

Practices to be avoided, identified by Lebanese ARU

#	Practice
1	Lack of international legal framework protecting refugees
2	Non accountable Roles and responsibilities for protecting refugees
3	No international instruments protecting refugees and building State asylum systems
4	Lack of monitoring and managing the border and regulating the entry of refugees

Mapping of formal and informal practices to be avoided with vulnerable typologies

The nine GPs to be avoided are addressed to: Children, Unaccompanied Children, People with disabilities, Elderly, Pregnancy Human Trafficking, Human Trafficking, Serious Illness, Mental disorders. For both Italy and

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Jordan, the Generic of practices to be avoided are not classified. For Spain, only, Unaccompanied Children were classified. For Finland, Hungary, Turkey, and Lebanon information of the GPs to be avoided are not available.

Note: Spain has also listed practices to be avoided that are not classified against listed typologies. The practices mainly dealt with the privatization of asylum seeker services and in case of minors, the increase of violation if the seekers are not provided with documentation or schooling.

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Conclusion

LIU had concentrated on attention and inclusion practices as well as the integration of contributions. All collected data were gathered from reports explained by the seven countries under investigation: Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan, and Lebanon. The selected methodology adopted to carry out these studies were aligned with the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) guidelines. Its research strategy was based on triangulation and data collected via mixed methods, and carried out through action, for meeting the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models.

The research team has worked as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units, through promoting the VG people's involvement, had gathered the necessary information, and test practices, and sustainable over time by creating an international observatory of TAIS. Work had relied on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining helped to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases.

This collected information was examined to generate helpful conclusions that led the whole project to identify the good practices. Mainly, the collected data were obtained by the ARUs of different countries and other stakeholders, in which each ARU carried out pilot studies, through action research. These tasks comprised identifying sources of information, gathering information artefacts, analysing of artefacts, characterising attention, and inclusion practices, and creating the catalogue of attention and inclusion practices for FDP in the EU influence area.

RAISD generated information, scientific knowledge, to solve specific problems, to succeed in practical applications for Vulnerable Groups among Forcibly Displaced People and hosting communities. The project sought for defining distinctively vulnerable groups (the VGs) among FDP. It was able to assess how different policies, laws and treaties are affecting attention and inclusion strategies towards VGs of FDP. Standards and principles were meaningful to all stakeholders involved in the project, which generated actor-oriented criterion.

The different policies affecting attention and inclusion towards VGs of FDP established by the seven investigated countries: Italy, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan, and Lebanon were compared. The policies of each country to see what criteria were adapted in defining the VGs were observed. Furthermore, to compare the different policies, laws and treaties that were legislated or agreed on in order to define VGs with all inclusion strategies.

The context of each country under research had a major effect on the policies, laws and treaties affecting attention and inclusion strategies towards VGs of FDP, through the identification of key criteria to evaluate strategies and practices for attention and inclusion of VGs of FDP. The seven countries that were analysed in terms of good practices were discussed in terms of the policies and laws applied for determining and catering to the basic needs of VGs (or VCs) and courses of actions to take, following data collection methods based on action research.

Five of the seven researched countries were states parties to the 1951 Geneva Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol. States parties to the Convention are required to protect refugees that are in their territory and to obey to the principle of "non-refoulement. In practice, however, the states

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parties to the Convention vary significantly in their receptivity to asylum seekers and the extent to which conflicting national policies affect adherence to norms prescribed in the Convention.

Asylum seekers are required to submit an asylum application to the country's competent authority. Different actions apply to different categories of applicants. The Convention permits divergent practices in the processing of applications. Screening requirements that involve collecting personal details, fingerprints, and photographs of the applicant are common. The determining authority typically examines submitted documentation and interviews the applicant. In addition, denied applicants commonly have the opportunity to appeal an adverse determination. Assistance to Asylum seekers includes housing, food, access to medical care, education, employment, travel documentation, and information about their legal rights.

The researchers presented a comparison between partners at the level of the implementation strategies was achieved. The comparison had addressed the implementation plan at the level of each type of VGs, in each of the seven countries. So, each of them was compared based on the implantations of good practices on how each of them dealt with refugees, asylum seekers, or VGs in order to analyse how, through these practices, they could best address their needs.

Since the criteria were not clear for all of partners in order to address their policies, the proposed actions were different. Based on that, and on how each country dealt with the VGs, it was recommended to use uniform VG criteria to specially address this

The researchers assessed *typology and characteristics, religious groups, and civil organizations* relating to each of the seven countries under research was carried out. Besides, a prototype inspired by UNHCR was developed in order to generate a pathway among civil organizations, which ultimately led to better empower VGs on many fronts such as, education, health, and social assistance.

According to the researchers, *firstly*, typology and characterization were implemented by religious groups, civil organization, unofficial groups, and neighbourhoods. They were formal in the sense that they had a plan (program or project) but did not have public or international funding. *Secondly*, four of the seven countries presented results showing similar religions groups were not totally considered in the previously stated countries. *Lastly*, worldwide assistance programs addressing VGs heavily rely on the work and practices of civil organizations.

Accordingly, to the work of civil organizations, data presented on five of the seven researched countries revealed that the civil organizations sector focused exclusively on the attention and inclusion of asylum seekers along with VGs. This should be coordinated with the UNHCR which closely coordinates the refugee status under the leading and collaborative efforts of governments in cooperation with the private sector. Finally, assistance and/or empowering programs were involved with vocational training, skills building programs, and entrepreneurship programs.

The researchers presented practices which revolved around the availability of specific adequate variables, such as, accessibility to quality education, inclusion in the workforce, housing and settlement, and social network along with gender sensitiveness, worldwide. Promising a commitment towards attaining valuable good practices

by VGs required governmental policies addressing their social and economic inclusion, as noticed by the researchers.

They discussed the practices to be avoided when addressing vulnerable groups (VGs). They noted that they were mostly related to the asylum procedures in most of the researched countries. In brief, the researchers pointed out that the practices to be avoided were those that were related to the unfair (or inequitable) policies relating to education, healthcare services, decent employment opportunities and social security. Whereas, the literature summed up some of those policies, and the resulting practices to be avoided.

The following part dealing with the comparisons of practices to be avoided, from each country. The researchers noted that due to the increasing number of refugees, the number of these centres became insufficient, and need to increase.

The following part entailed a comparison of good practices across each of the seven investigated countries. As a result, after going over all identified good practices, the researchers also noted that there was no unanimous definition of “good practices” between all countries. As each one approached them from its own different perspective, with many intersections, in terms of helping, assisting, mentoring, educating, and providing services to refugees and VGs.

The researchers went over and analysed the recommendations or proposals from all countries’ presented programs, through the following observations: 1) there are no specific common aspects across the recommendations of all countries. 2) There was a common terminology to be used by all concerned countries. 3) Recommendations of some countries intersect in terms of generic programs such humanitarian helped, services to refugees.

Through the careful examination and analysis of the different practices to avoid, the researchers had the following observations:

- A great deal of difference was observed among practices identified by different countries.
- It is clear that the stakeholders did not follow a common procedure for the identification of practices to be avoided.
- For each country, it is not obvious which ultimate goal the proposed practices to be avoided serve.
- These practices were proposed based on the feedback and experience of the stakeholders with different vulnerable groups taking into consideration the context, and the situation of the different VGs.

The researchers then presented the search for criteria which evaluated the policies and practices of attention towards VGs and FDP. Yet, not all the partners provided clear criteria for the evaluation process.

The different indicators that were provided by some of the researched countries, through evaluations of their respective evaluation criteria were those that were provided to the researchers, since not all countries provided them. *For instance, Italy, one of the seven infatuated countries, had provided help the recipients to build a perception of their employability and increased their autonomy in searching for opportunities after the conclusion of the apprenticeship.*

The researchers provided, backed up by thorough and specific analysis enriched with literature review, that the prerogatives addressed for each country regarding the evaluation criteria were set. However, they noticed that these evaluation processes were still not clear, as they had different perspectives. Nevertheless, the common points that the researchers came up with, was that the quality of services afforded and empowerment of the VGs.

According to the researchers, an attempt was made to reach a threshold for the minimum standards. Thus, the criteria for each country were presented, where, the common criteria for the evaluation of the practices were based on categories of VGs, quality and context of the practices were reviewed by the researchers. So, the minimum standards for dealing with VGs was to focus on collecting information from the VGs, the classification of information based on the different types of VGs and provided quality type of practices.

The following observations were made:

- The process of identification of stakeholders that made an identification of the practice is not described by each country.
- The process of identification, selection, and characterization of the practices is not well established.
- Practices are recommended to be characterized in terms of addressed needs, target groups diversification, specific goal, scope or level of impact and typology of intervention.
- The interviews with a large population of vulnerable groups represented the bedrock of the process of identification of practices.
- Identified practices did not tackle all classified VGs, which was due to the lack of a common process for the identification and characterization of practices.

A careful examination of the formal and informal practices to be avoided, as listed by each country was carried out by the researchers. It became clear they were not developed based on a well-defined procedure context or common criteria.

Selection criteria were established for a successful and fruitful communication with all identified VGs (or VCs). Getting in direct contact with these groups favoured a realistic selection, listing, and classification of the practices to be avoided. As a result, in conclusion, a large number of VGs was involved to cover as many practices to avoid (which are...) as possible.

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